

TEACHING METHODOLOGY OF THE RUSSIAN LANGUAGE IN HIGH SCHOOL IN THE ERA OF DIGITALIZATION

F.R. Ibragimova

Teacher of the department “Uzbek and Russian language and literature”, Urgench state pedagogical institute

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Abstract. *This article explores scientific and methodological approaches to teaching the Russian language in high school within the context of education digitalization. It analyzes promising pedagogical technologies and digital tools that contribute to enhancing the effectiveness of learning. Special attention is given to the integration of traditional and digital methods, as well as the development of students' cross-disciplinary competencies and media literacy. The article substantiates the need to adapt the teacher's role and update teaching materials in accordance with the modern requirements of the digital educational environment. This study is of interest to educators, methodologists, and educational resource developers.*

Keywords: *educational digitalization, scientific and methodological approaches, digital technologies, distance learning, digital resources, pedagogical innovations, media literacy, educational platform.*

Introduction

Digitalization of education is one of the defining trends of modern times, deeply influencing all aspects of learning, including teaching Russian in high school. Rapid development of digital technologies transforms the forms of presenting educational material, methods of interaction between teacher and pupils, lesson structure, as well as approaches to knowledge assessment. Teaching Russian in senior classes, aimed at forming complex linguistic and speech skills, developing analytical thinking and text interpretation abilities, requires adaptation to new realities. Therefore, this article is dedicated to analyzing scientific and methodological approaches to teaching Russian in senior classes within the digital educational environment. The goal is to identify and evaluate the effectiveness of both traditional and innovative pedagogical practices and to develop recommendations for their optimal adaptation.

The relevance of this topic is confirmed by active discussion on modernizing Russian teaching methods in senior classes in current scientific-pedagogical literature. Increasing attention is given to integrating digital technologies into the educational process and rethinking traditional methodological approaches.

The theoretical basis for forming communicative, linguistic, and textual competencies in pupils was laid in the works of classical methodologists such as V. A. Krutetsky, L. V. Shcherba, and T. A. Ladyzhenskaya. In the context of digital transformation of education, their approaches receive new understanding and adaptation to modern realities.

Contemporary researchers, including E. I. Passov, M. R. Lvov, and N. A. Shchukina, emphasize the significance of learner-centered and activity-based approaches in teaching, which become especially relevant when using digital tools that ensure individualization and variability of the educational process.

Issues of organizing the digital educational environment as a space for developing key competencies and creating new forms of teacher-pupil interaction are examined in the works of E. S. Polat, I. V. Robert, and A. V. Khutorsky. Special attention is paid to organizing blended and distance learning, using interactive platforms, educational apps, and online services.

An important contribution to understanding the role of digital technologies in education comes from research on digital didactics and media literacy by A. V. Grebenyuk, O. E. Lebedeva, and N. V. Makarova, where the necessity of forming pupils' skills for critical information work and effective use of digital resources in learning and project activities is substantiated.

Thus, analysis of modern scientific-methodological literature shows an active search for new approaches to integrating digital technologies into teaching Russian in senior classes, aimed at providing quality education in a dynamically developing educational environment.

Consequently, digitalization requires teachers to comprehensively revise traditional Russian language teaching methods and actively implement innovative approaches. When used competently, modern technologies become a powerful tool to increase pupils' motivation, develop their communicative and cognitive skills, and prepare them for full participation in the information society.

The current stage of educational development is characterized by active implementation of digital technologies, which naturally entails reconsidering established scientific-methodological approaches to teaching, including Russian in senior classes. In new conditions, the priority is not just knowledge transmission but forming pupils' universal learning activities, critical thinking, media literacy, and the ability to independently search, analyze, and process information. Therefore, it is important to consider key scientific-methodological approaches that are either already actively used or require adaptation to the digital educational environment.

The communicative approach, traditionally foundational in teaching Russian, acquires new forms and opportunities in the digital age. Active use of forums, chats, educational blogs, and video platforms promotes development of oral and written speech skills. Pupils get opportunities to participate in online discussions, create podcasts, presentations, and videos, which deepens lexical and grammatical work and helps effectively practice argumentation and coherent speech [9.C.55-64], [6.C.245-290].

The digital educational environment offers wide possibilities for implementing activity- and project-based learning effectively. Involving senior pupils in creating various digital products such as interactive maps, infographics, videos, text and multimedia publications activates their cognitive activity and supports development of cross-disciplinary competencies. Organizing project work online allows pupils to work individually and in groups, developing collaboration and self-organization skills [7.C.102-110].

Using digital platforms like "YaKlass," "RESH," Moodle, Google Classroom, etc., considerably facilitates implementing the learner-centered approach, allowing consideration of each pupil's individual features. Adaptive learning paths, instant feedback, and the possibility to independently choose additional resources enable addressing preparation level, motivation, and pace of material assimilation for each pupil [3. C.47-55].

Interactive technologies such as online tests, quizzes, quests, game trainers, and mind maps are particularly valuable in teaching Russian. These tools make learning more engaging, stimulate active pupil participation, and improve involvement levels. Digital tools are especially effective for complex topics like syntax, morphology, spelling, and speech norms [4.C.45-52].

One priority in modern education is forming media literacy. Russian lessons can and should be a platform for analyzing media texts, studying linguistic manipulation techniques, recognizing fake news and advertising. Using various internet materials helps pupils apply linguistic knowledge practically, develop critical thinking, and information security skills [8.C.22-30].

Digitalization does not diminish but transforms the teacher's role. The teacher ceases to be the sole information source and becomes an organizer, tutor, and mentor, guiding pupils on their individual educational paths. Consequently, teachers' digital competencies increase in importance: their ability to select quality educational resources, design a modern digital educational environment, and use its possibilities effectively to achieve goals [2. C.12-18], [5.C.47], [1.C.57].

Based on the analysis of scientific-methodological approaches to teaching Russian in senior classes under digitalization, the following key outcomes can be formulated:

Use of modern digital tools and educational platforms enhances pupil motivation, activates cognitive activity, and leads to more effective language material assimilation. Interactive exercises, multimedia resources, and online communication opportunities expand practical Russian use.

Classical approaches — communicative, activity-based, and learner-centered — remain relevant and effective when adapted and organically integrated with digital technologies, creating flexible educational trajectories that account for individual needs.

Digitalization fosters formation of not only language skills but also universal competencies such as media literacy, critical thinking, effective information handling, and productive communication in digital environments.

The teacher's role in the digital environment changes significantly, requiring new skills and competencies. The teacher becomes a guide and supporter rather than just a knowledge source.

Along with advantages, digitalization entails risks like potential decline in oral speech quality, cognitive overload, and technical and social barriers needing attention in organizing education.

This study confirms that educational digitalization presents challenges and broad prospects for improving Russian language teaching methods in senior classes.

Analysis shows that integrating digital technologies effectively improves language learning quality and develops key meta-subject competencies, including media literacy, critical thinking, and learning independence.

Successful digital tool adoption requires careful adaptation of traditional methods, considering the digital educational environment and each pupil's individual characteristics. The teacher plays a key role in transforming from knowledge transmitter to qualified mentor supporting pupils on their educational path.

Conclusion

Thus, scientific-methodological approaches to teaching Russian in the digital era should be based on harmoniously combining classical pedagogical principles and advanced digital technologies. This approach ensures comprehensive development of pupils' language personalities and prepares them for successful communication and effective activity in the modern information society.

Prospective research directions include developing and testing innovative digital methodological materials and technologies and deepening the study of their impact on education quality and pupils' speech competence formation.

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